

EMOTIONAL MATURITY AND ATTITUDE AMONG HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

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Abstract:

Emotional Maturity is said to be the foundation for leading a happy and contented life. If anyone lacks Emotional Maturity the life of the individual will be a sorrowful affair. Higher Secondary stage seems to be the formative stage. Lot of opportunities and avenues are there to get them emotionally disturbed. The events and incidents projected in the media portrays how the youth of today are fall as victims in the name of modernity and spoiling their life due to emotional imbalance. This motivates the Investigator to conduct a study on Emotional Maturity and Attitude towards Schooling of Higher Secondary Students particularly in Theni District.

Key Words: Emotional Imbalance, Modernity, Victims Etc

Introduction:

It is often noticed that the inability to manage emotions or communicate effectively often lead to unresolved and repetitive conflict among learners. With the recent advancements in neuroscience, it is known that the emotional centres of the brain are intricate inter-woven with the neo-cortical areas involved in cognitive learning. When a child is caught up with distressing emotional, the centres for learning are temporarily hampered. The child’s attention becomes pre-occupied and truly lesser ability to hear to understand or to remember what the teacher or the book is saying. In short, there is a direct link between emotions and learning. The higher secondary students are often feel betrayed by the family, neighbourhood, community and society. So, it is important to analyse their problems for paving good opportunity and atmosphere for healthy learning.

Objectives of the Study:

- The following objectives are formulated for the present study
- ✓ To measure the level of Emotional maturity among the higher secondary students.
 - ✓ To measure the level of attitude towards schooling among the higher secondary students.
 - ✓ To find out the relationship between emotional maturity and attitude towards schooling among the higher secondary students.
 - ✓ To find out the significant influence of independent variable viz., Sex, Medium Of Instruction, School Locality, School Kind, School Management, Tuition Undergoing, Family Income, Parents Education Level, Participation In Extra- Curricular Activities and Participation In Sports and Games on dependent variable emotional maturity.

Methodology in Brief:

Sample:

A sample of 300 higher secondary students served as the subjects of the study. The present study was basically designed as a descriptive one with normative and survey as the method and technique of research employed for data collection.

Tools Used:

- ✓ Personal Information Schedule
- ✓ Emotional Maturity Scale Constructed and Standardized by Sathiyagirirajan, S., (2010)
- ✓ Attitude towards schooling scale Constructed and Standardized by Rajesh Kumar, K (2013)

Statistical Treatment:

- ✓ Mean
- ✓ Standard Deviation
- ✓ “t” test between the large independent samples.
- ✓ Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation

Hypothesis 1:

Emotional Maturity and Attitude towards Schooling has significant positive relationship. Result of relationship of Emotional Maturity with attitude towards schooling among the higher secondary students is presented in table 1.

Table 1: Correlation of Emotional Maturity with attitude towards Schooling among the Higher Secondary Students

Variables	Correlation Coefficient (r)
	Total N = 300
Emotional Maturity with Attitude Towards Schooling	0.0031*

* Denotes Significant at 0.05 level

The above table 1 shows that the calculated value 'r', 0.0031 is less than the critical value i.e 0.05774. Hence the Emotional Intelligence has no relationship with attitude towards schooling among the higher secondary students

Hypothesis 2:

There is a significant difference in the Emotional Maturity among the higher secondary students in terms of School Locality. The statistical measures and the results of test of significance of difference between the mean scores of Emotional Maturity among the higher secondary students in terms of School Locality are presented in table 2.

Table 2: Statistical Measures and Results of Test of Significance for Difference Between the Means of Emotional Maturity: School Locality Wise

Variable	Sub-Variables	N	Mean	SD	't' - Value	Significance At 0.05 Level
School Locality	Urban	150	44.893	3.109	5.073	Significant
	Rural	150	43.127	2.920		

The obtained 't' value 5.073 is higher than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference in Emotional Maturity among the higher secondary students in terms of School Locality. Further, it is observed that students studying in the schools located in urban schools have high level of Emotional Maturity than the students studying in the schools located in rural schools.

Figure 1: Means of Emotional Maturity: School Locality Wise

Hypothesis 3:

There is a significant difference in the Emotional Maturity among the higher secondary students in terms of School Kind. The statistical measures and the results of test of significance of difference between the mean scores of Emotional Maturity among the higher secondary students in terms of School Kind are presented in table 3.

Table 3: Statistical Measures and Results of Test of Significance for Difference Between the Means of Emotional Maturity: School Kind Wise

Variable	Sub - Variables	N	Mean	SD	'T' - Value	Significance At 0.05 Level
School Kind	UNISEX	50	44.860	2.474	2.110	Significant
	CO-ED	250	43.840	3.232		

The obtained 't' value 2.110 is higher than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference in Emotional Maturity among the higher secondary students in terms of School Kind. Further, it is observed that students studying in the unisex schools have high level of Emotional Maturity than the students studying in the co-ed schools. Hence the hypothesis 3 is accepted.

Figure 2: Means of Emotional Maturity: School Kind – Wise

Conclusions:

The major conclusions emerged out of the present study are presented below. Emotional Maturity among the higher secondary students is found to be low. Attitude towards schooling is found to be high. Further,

it is observed that Emotional Maturity of the higher secondary students have no relationship with Attitude towards Schooling. Students studying in urban schools have higher level of Emotional maturity. Students studying in unisex schools have higher level of Emotional maturity. In general, there is no significant difference in the attitude towards schooling among the higher secondary students irrespective of the ten personal valuables studied in the present investigation.

Educational Implications:

It is quite interesting to observe that the present investigation has revealed that the students studying in the unisex schools and urban schools have higher level of Emotional Maturity. It can further be derived that the students have high level, in other words favourable attitude towards schooling. Government has to take necessary plan to conduct psychological program through Institutions with the concerned experts to enhance the Emotional Maturity among the higher secondary students.

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